

Comparison Between Platelet Rich Plasma (PRP) Injections and Corticosteroids for the Treatment of Chronic Plantar Fasciitis

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Plantar fasciitis is a common cause of heel pain. It is a clinical diagnosis, with patients classically experiencing particularly severe pain with the first few steps in the morning. Although it is often a self-limiting condition, the severity of the pain warrants medical attention. Symptoms will subside more quickly if risk factors are addressed and various treatment approaches are initiated as soon as possible.

Objective: The aim of this study was to evaluate and compare the clinical effectiveness of platelet-rich plasma (PRP) versus corticosteroid (Cs) injections in the treatment of chronic plantar fasciitis.

Methods: This prospective randomized comparative study was conducted over 12 months at Ghazi Al-Hariri Hospital and Baghdad Medical City. The study included 40 patients with chronic plantar fasciitis (symptoms > 3 months) who had failed conservative therapy. Participants were randomly assigned to two groups:

Group I (PRP): Received 5–6 ml of PRP.

Group II (Cs): Received 40 mg of methylprednisolone.

Pain was evaluated using the Numeric Pain Rating Scale (NPRS) at rest and during movement at baseline, 1 day, 10 days, and 1 month post-injection.

Results: Both groups demonstrated a significant reduction in pain scores and improved functional outcomes as time progressed. While pain decreased in both cohorts, the corticosteroid group experienced a more rapid improvement compared to the PRP group. A statistically significant difference favoring the steroid group was found at 10 days post-injection during movement ($p=0.02$). However, by the one-month follow-up, no statistically significant difference in pain relief was observed between the two groups. Additionally, the study noted that female gender and higher body weight were associated with significantly higher pain scores.

Conclusion: Both PRP and corticosteroid injections are effective treatments for providing symptomatic relief in chronic plantar fasciitis. Corticosteroids appear to offer faster short-term pain reduction, particularly within the first 10 days following intervention.

KEYWORDS: Chronic plantar fasciitis, Platelet rich plasma, Corticosteroid injection.

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INTRODUCTION

Plantar fasciitis (PFs) is the pain caused by degenerative irritation at the insertion of the plantar fascia (PF) on the medial process of the calcaneal tuberosity. The pain may be substantial, resulting in the alteration of daily activities.^[1] Despite its name, plantar fasciitis has a degenerative rather

than inflammatory nature and is related to overuse trauma leading to microtears^[2]; thus, the term “plantar fasciopathy” is often preferred. Chronic plantar fasciitis (CPF) is the most common cause of chronic heel pain in adults, affecting both young active patients and older more sedentary individuals.^[3] Possible risk factors include female, obesity, pregnancy, occupations requiring prolonged standing and weight-

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bearing, and heel spurs. Other risk factors may be broadly classified as either extrinsic (training errors and equipment) or intrinsic (functional, structural, or degenerative).^[4]

Corticosteroid (Cs) injections to the plantar fascia have commonly been used in recalcitrant cases of plantar fasciitis, where conservative therapies have failed to bring about relief.^[5] Whether or not injected corticosteroids alter the long term pathology of chronic inflammation, many patients experience acute symptomatic improvement. Cs injection may be given through a plantar or a medial approach with or without ultrasound guidance, typically in conjunction with a local anesthetic.^[6] Avoid injecting within the superficial layers of the subcutaneous tissue, because Cs injection into the superficial fat pad can cause fat necrosis and atrophy, which reduce the shock absorbing capacity of the plantar heel.^[7]

PRP, similar to other regenerative medicine modalities, aims to repair damaged or worn out tissue. The mechanisms of the repair continue to be explored. It is established that the primary role of PRP is not replacement of the damaged or worn off tissue, but rather facilitation of tissue recovery by signaling and recruiting mesenchymal stem cells. It appears that PRP contains significantly more growth factors and other signaling molecules than are typically present in the affected tissue or, even, in the whole blood.^[8]

Aim of study

The aim of this study is to evaluate and compare the effectiveness of platelet rich plasma (PRP) and corticosteroid injections in chronic cases of plantar fasciitis.

Patients and methods

a prospective randomized comparative clinical study comparing PRP and CS injections for plantar fasciitis. This study was carried out for a period of 12 Months from October 2020 to first of November 2021. This study was done in the Department Of Pain Management of Ghazi Al-Hariri Hospital for Specialized Surgery and Baghdad Medical City, and all participants signed an informed consent, (male and female) and selected according to specific criteria.

Inclusion Criteria:

- >18 years old, (18-70) years old
- Patients with chronic PF pain (>3 months).
- Patients not responding to conservative treatments as ice, rest, stretching, anti-inflammatory medication and physical therapy for more than 3 months.
- Patients with severe pain.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patient refusal
- Recent use of corticosteroids and NSAIDs during last 2 months
- Recent trauma to heel.
- Immunocompromised patients due to liability for infection.
- Recent febrile or infectious disease.

- Peripheral neuropathy related to heel pain.
- Pregnancy in corticosteroid group.
- Local infection at the site of the procedure.
- History of any malignancy (including hematologic & non-hematologic malignancies).
- Had hematological disorder like anemia (hemoglobin < 7.0 g/dl), thrombocytopenia (platelets < 15,000/IL) or bleeding dyscrasias.

The collection of data was kept confidential and not be divulged except for the purpose of the study.

The Participant's agreement will be considered and they will be informed that the participation is voluntary and they can withdraw from the study after having agreed to participate.

Including 40 patients with chronic plantar fasciitis who attended into clinic of pain relief in Ghazi Al-Hariri Hospital for Specialized Surgery and Baghdad Medical City .

They were randomly classified into 2 groups according to their treatment method, each group included 20 patients using a simple randomization method (odd for PRP and even for steroid) by the researchers who injected the patients with either steroids or PRP (guided by ultrasound):

- Group I (PRP) was injected (5-6) ml PRP (Plasma Components) after local anesthetic injection.
- group II (Cs) was injected methylprednisolone (40 mg/10ml) with total volume (6-10 ml) with local anesthesia according to the spread.

All the patients operated by the same team, a standard medication package was administered to all patients pretherapy.

Pre-injection all patients of our study were subjected to full history taking, thorough physical examination, visual analog scale (VAS) , complete blood count (CBC) to exclude anemia and thrombocytopenia, plain X-ray to detect calcaneal spur, and ultrasonography to measure plantar fascia thickness.

Patients were reassessed by Numeric Pain Rating Scale (NPRS) at 1st day ,10 days and 1 month post-injection. Sonographic examination was performed with 5–12 MHZ linear array transducer on both symptomatic and asymptomatic heels.

The patients lay prone and their ankles dorsiflexed to 90 degree. The thickness of the PF was measured on the longitudinal view of the heel from the anterior edge of the inferior calcaneal border. PFs was defined as plantar fascia thickness >4 mm or when there was >1 mm difference in plantar fascia thickness between symptomatic and asymptomatic heels in association of reduced echogenicity and/or loss of definition of border of the fascia distal to the antero-inferior border of the calcaneus.

A structured questionnaire is the base for data collection developed by the researcher and reviewed by the supervisor and it is consisting of;

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- The demographic information includes: code NO., age , sex , duration of disease , address and phone number.
- Disease information including: patient complain, duration, grade of disease , past medical history and past drug history.

After injection patients were scheduled for follow up visits after 10 day and one month. At each visits pain scale was measured using (Numeric Pain Rating Scale) (NPRS). Evaluation of pain was performed by a physician blinded to the patient group and were recorded in a specified data sheet for right and left foot during rest and movement.

Data was translated into a computerized database structure. Statistical analyses was done using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences). Version 20 computer software for

windows. Categorical variables were presented as frequency and percentage , Chi-square was used to test the significance of the association between categorical variables .with considered P. Value of ≤ 0.05 was statistically significant.

RESULTS

The current study included 40 patients with chronic planter fasciitis, 20 of them were underwent PRP injection to be compared with (20 patients) underwent steroid injection. The results revealed that the age of the patients ranged between 30 to 70 years with a mean age was 46.58 ± 9.886 years and the mean weight of study sample was 85.75 ± 6.709 and without any significant difference in age, weight and height was shown between the two groups (table 1).

Table 1: Distribution of study sample according sociodemographic characteristic.

Variable	PRP Mean \pm SD	STEROID Mean \pm SD	P value
AGE	45.9 ± 9.722	47.25 ± 10.25	0.672
Weight (kg)	87.40 ± 6.613	84.10 ± 6.553	0.121
Height (cm)	167.85 ± 4.660	165.35 ± 5.815	0.142
BMI	31.04 ± 2.29	30.83 ± 2.90	0.810

The majority of the patients included in the study were female 25 (62.5%) and 75% of female were treated with steroid injection but without any statistically significant association between gender and groups as shown in (table 2).

Table 2: Sex distribution of study sample.

SEX	PRP	STEROID	TOTAL	P value
Female	10 (50%)	15 (75%)	25(62.5%)	0.102
Male	10 (50%)	5(25%)	15(37.5%)	
Total	20(100%)	20(100%)	40(100%)	

Regarding to correlation between study groups and pain score at movement, the result of study showed the mean score of pain in baseline among PRP and steroid groups were (8.40 ± 1.142 and 8.60 ± 0.99 respectively), while after first day,10 days and one month after injection, the result found decrease in pain score in two groups but more among steroid group than PRP group with statistically significant association in ten days only at movement ($p=0.02$), as showed in (table 3) and (figure 1).

Table 3: Distribution of study sample according to pain score at movement.

Pain score at movement	PRP Mean \pm SD	STEROID Mean \pm SD	P value
Before injection	8.40 ± 1.142	8.60 ± 0.995	0.287
1 st day after injection	7.05 ± 1.504	6.30 ± 1.867	0.176
After 10 days	4.60 ± 1.635	3.75 ± 2.511	0.02
After 1 month	2.55 ± 1.932	2.75 ± 2.124	0.441

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Figure 1: Distribution of study sample according to pain score at movement.

Regarding to correlation between study groups and pain score at rest the result of study showed the mean score of pain in baseline among PRP and steroid groups were (2.35 ± 1.694 and 3.05 ± 2.235 respectively), after first day and ten days the result found decrease in pain score in two groups but more

among steroid groups while after one month the mean score of pain more decrease among PRP group than steroid group but without statistically differences as showed in (table 4) and (figure 2).

Table 4: Distribution of study sample according to pain score at rest.

Pain score at rest	PRP Mean \pm SD	STERIOD Mean \pm SD	P value
Before injection	2.35 ± 1.694	3.05 ± 2.235	0.424
1 st day after injection	1.60 ± 1.603	1.25 ± 1.517	0.959
After 10 days	0.95 ± 1.395	0.80 ± 1.152	0.410
After 1 month	0.60 ± 1.273	0.70 ± 1.129	0.695

Figure 2: Distribution of study sample according to pain score at rest.

Regarding to correlation between gender and pain score (at movement, and rest) the result of study showed the mean score of pain among male lower than female, with statistically

significant association, as showed in (table 5 and 6) respectively.

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Table 5: Relationship between Pain score at movement and gender.

Pain score at movement	Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	P value
Before injection	female	25	8.76	1.012	0.044
	male	15	8.07	1.033	
1 st day after injection	female	25	6.88	1.833	0.336
	male	15	6.33	1.496	
After 10 days	female	25	4.68	2.212	0.052
	male	15	3.33	1.759	
After 1 month	female	25	3.2	2.102	0.032
	male	15	1.73	1.486	

Table 6: Relationship between Pain score at rest and gender.

Pain score at rest	Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	P value
Before injection	female	25	3.24	2.107	0.025
	male	15	1.8	1.424	
1 st day after injection	female	25	1.84	1.7	0.014
	male	15	0.73	0.961	
After 10 days	female	25	1.24	1.393	0.016
	male	15	0.27	0.704	
After 1 month	female	25	0.96	1.369	0.031
	male	15	0.13	0.516	

regarding to correlation between weight and pain score at (movement, and rest) in both groups the result of study showed there are statistically significant association between

weight and the mean score as showed in table (7) and (8) respectively.

Table 7: Relationship between Pain score at movement and weight.

Variables	Mean	Std. D.	P value
Pain score at movement (Before injection)	8.5	1.062	0.001
Weight:(kg)	85.75	6.709	
Pain score at movement (1st day after injection)	6.68	1.716	0.001
Weight:(kg)	85.75	6.709	
Pain score at movement (After 10 days)	4.18	2.135	0.001
Weight:(kg)	85.75	6.709	
Pain score at rest. (After 1 month)	2.65	2.007	0.001
Weight:(kg)	85.75	6.709	

Table 8: Relationship between Pain score at rest and weight.

Variables	Mean	Std. D.	P value
Pain score at rest (Before injection)	2.7	1.99	0.001
Weight:(kg)	85.75	6.709	
Pain score at rest (1st day after injection)	1.43	1.551	0.001
Weight:(kg)	85.75	6.709	
Pain score at rest (After 10 days)	0.88	1.265	0.001
Weight:(kg)	85.75	6.709	
Pain score at rest (After 1 month)	0.65	1.189	0.001
Weight:(kg)	85.75	6.709	

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The result of present study found 60% of PRP group have calcaneal spur, while 55% of steroid group haven't calcaneal spur and without any statistically difference ($p=0.324$). Also, the associated nerve entrapment double among PRP group than steroid and without statistically significant ($p=0.548$), regarding to plantar fascia thickening that diagnosis by U/S,

the result showed no any statistically significant association between study groups ($p=0.744$). Also the result of study found no any correlation between the previous injection and study groups. As shown in (table 9).

Table 9: Relationship between study groups and disease characteristic.

Variables	Groups		Total	P value
	PRP	STEROID		
X-ray calcaneal Spur				
No	8 (40%)	11(55%)	19(47.5%)	0.324
Yes	12 (60%)	9 (45%)	21(52.5%)	
Total	20(100%)	20(100%)	40(100%)	
Associated nerve entrapment				
No	18(90%)	19(95%)	37(92.5%)	0.548
Yes	2(10%)	1(5%)	3(7.5%)	
Total	20(100%)	20(100%)	40(100%)	
Plantar fascia thickening U/S				
YES	13(65%)	12(60%)	25(62.5%)	0.744
NO	7(35%)	8(40%)	15(37.5%)	
Total	20(100%)	20(100%)	40(100%)	
Previous injection				
No	12(60%)	16(80%)	28(70%)	0.301
Yes	8(40%)	4(20%)	12(30%)	
Total	20(100%)	20(100%)	40(100%)	

The result of the current study showed a decrease in the average degree of pain at rest after 1 day and 10 days of injection among the PRP group, as well as its decrease after 1 month but less than before with a statistically difference between them (p value less than 0.05), as shown in (table 10) and (figure 3). Furthermore, the result found a greater

reduction in the mean pain score at movement between the PRP group after 1 day and 10 days after injection while we see a more than doubling decrease in pain score after 1 month, with a statistically significant association ($P < 0.05$). As shown in (table 11) and (figure 4).

Table 10: comparison of pain score at rest among PRP group.

Pairs	PRP GROUP (PAIN SCORE AT REST)	N	Mean	St. Deviation	P VALUE
Pair 1	(Before injection)	20	2.35	1.694	0.003
	(1st day after injection)	20	1.6	1.603	
Pair 2	(Before injection)	20	2.35	1.694	0.001
	(After 10 days)	20	0.95	1.395	
Pair 3	(Before injection)	20	2.35	1.694	0.001
	(After 1 month)	20	0.6	1.273	
Pair 4	(After 10 days)	20	0.95	1.395	0.031
	(After 1 month)	20	0.6	1.273	

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Figure 3: liner mean of pain score at rest among PRP group.

Table 11: comparison of pain score at movement among PRP group.

Pairs	PRP GROUP (PAIN SCORE AT MOVEMENT)	N	Mean	St. Deviation	P VALUE
Pair 1	(Before injection)	20	8.4	1.142	0.001
	(1st day after injection)	20	7.05	1.504	
Pair 2	(Before injection)	20	8.4	1.142	0.001
	(After 10 days)	20	4.6	1.635	
Pair 3	(Before injection)	20	8.4	1.142	<0.001
	(After 1 month)	20	2.55	1.932	
Pair 4	(After 10 days)	20	4.6	1.635	<0.001
	(After 1 month)	20	2.55	1.932	

Figure 4: liner mean of pain score at movement among PRP group.

The result of the current study showed a decrease in the mean score of pain at rest after 1 day and 10 days of injection among the steroid group, as well as its decrease after 1 month but less than before and without a statically difference between them ($p = 0.163$), as shown in table 12 and figure 5.

In addition to that, the result showed more reduction in the mean pain score on movement between the steroid group after 1 day ,10 days and one month after injection , with a statistically significant association ($P < 0.05$). As shown in Table 13 and Figure 6.

Table 12: comparison of pain score at rest among steroid group.

Pairs	Steroid Group (Pain Score At Rest)	N	Mean	St. Deviation	P VALUE
Pair 1	(Before injection)	20	3.05	2.235	0.001
	(1st day after injection)	20	1.25	1.517	
Pair 2	(Before injection)	20	3.05	2.235	<0.001
	(After 10 days)	20	0.8	1.152	

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Pair 3	(Before injection)	20	3.05	2.235	<0.001
	(After 1 month)	20	0.7	1.129	
Pair 4	(After 10 days)	20	0.8	1.152	0.163
	(After 1 month)	20	0.7	1.129	

Figure 5: liner mean of pain score at rest among steroid group.

Table 13: comparison of pain score at movement among steroid group.

Pairs	Steroid Group (Pain Score At Movement)	N	Mean	St. Deviation	P VALUE
Pair 1	(Before injection)	20	8.6	0.995	<0.001
	(1st day after injection)	20	6.3	1.867	
Pair 2	(Before injection)	20	8.6	0.995	<0.001
	(After 10 days)	20	3.75	2.511	
Pair 3	(Before injection)	20	8.6	0.995	<0.0001
	(After 1 month)	20	2.75	2.124	
Pair 4	(After 10 days)	20	3.75	2.511	0.001
	(After 1 month)	20	2.75	2.124	

Figure 6: liner mean of pain score at movement among steroid group.

DISCUSSION

Plantar fasciitis is one of the most common causes of heel pain that an orthopedist encounters in a medical clinic. It's degenerative disease rather from the inflammatory process and in chronic forms it can proved to be difficult to treat. Microscopic tears occur in the plantar fascia due to the windlass mechanism that exists. This is a combination of repeated opposing forces that act on the fascia by the action of the tendoachilles and the forefoot. This results in a cumulative cellular damage that is exaggerated by chaotic

vascularity. The fascia develops zones of hyperplasia and hypoplasia [9]. Various modalities employed for treating plantar fasciitis conservatively are night splinting, orthotics and stretching exercises. Corticosteroids injections have been used to treat plantar fasciitis and are an effective modality for pain relief. More Literatures has shown evidence of complications associated with corticosteroids injections such as fascial rupture. PRP due to its autologous nature is thought to be a safer alternative with less effect on the biochemical function of the foot [10]. This study will help us in deter which

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amongst the two treatments is more effective, so we compared two groups of patients with planter fasciitis, the first treated with steroid and the second treated with PRP. The mean age was 45.9 ± 9.722 years among PRP group while 47.25 ± 10.25 years among steroid group and without any statistically significant difference in age between the two groups. This result similar to study conducted by Ferhat S. et al.^[11] that showed the mean age in PRP was 47 ± 6.8 and 48.6 ± 6.4 among steroid group without any statistically difference. Another study by Soraganvi P. et al.^[12] found the mean age of the patients in Group A (PRP) and Group B (steroid) was 40.27 and 39.35 years, respectively and without statistically significant. In present study we found that both in the Corticosteroid and PRP group there was a decrease in the pain and increase in the function as time progressed from the first visit and follow up period ((at 1st day, 10 days and 1 month)). This was observed by the decreasing the pain Score at rest and movement in both the groups. But we see the mean of pain score decrease more and rapid in steroid group than PRP group but without any statistically significant among two groups at rest and movement except there was statistically significant association in 10 days only after intervention at movement ($p=0.02$), as showed in (table 3) and (figure 1). Literatures on treatment options show a variable outcome when PRP and steroid injection are used in the treatment of chronic plantar fasciitis. Some studies found PRP to be more effective whereas others did not find a significant difference in the outcome.^[13] When steroid injection was compared with autologous PRP injection in a study by Lee et al.^[14] they found that the corticosteroid group at (six weeks) after injection had significantly lower VAS than autologous PRP group. Karimzadeh et al comparing autologous PRP and corticosteroid local injection in treatment of plantar fasciitis concluded that variables of pain and function improved significantly in both corticosteroid and autologous PRP groups compared to control group. At 4 weeks following treatment, patients in corticosteroid group had significantly lower levels of pain than patients in autologous PRP and control groups.^[15] Mahindra et al found that there was a significant improvement in visual analog scale score in the platelet-rich plasma and corticosteroid groups at 3 weeks and at 3-month follow-up. Platelet-rich plasma injection is as effective as or more effective than corticosteroid injection in treating chronic plantar fasciitis.^[16] PRP contains a more concentrated amount of platelets than does whole blood. Within platelets are powerful growth factors, including platelet-derived growth factor, transforming growth factor beta, and epidermal growth factor. The injection of PRP into the affected tissue initiates the healing stages necessary to reverse the degenerative process at the base of the plantar fascia. The individual cytokines present in the platelet granules have been shown to enhance fibroblast migration and proliferation, up-regulate vascularization and increase

collagen deposition in a variety of in vitro and in vivo settings.^[17] The injection was administered at the point of maximum tender points. Jain et al in their study comparing single injection of PRP and steroid injection in chronic plantar fasciitis, found no significant difference in functional outcome in both groups at six months follow-up.^[18] In Soraganvi P. et al.^[12] study, observed that in both PRP and steroid injection group, VAS score improved after one injection and improvement in pain score was more in the steroid group compared to PRP group at first follow-up visit. On later follow-up VAS score in PRP group continued to improve and at the end of six months follow-up the PRP group showed better improvement compared to steroid group and improvement in score was statistically significant. The decline in pain and function scores of steroid groups after six weeks suggest that steroid injection is more effective only for short-term relief. The mechanism of reduction in pain and improvement in the function after PRP injection is not clear. other results that were obtained by Ertugrul Akşahin, et al. and Shetty VD, et al. who concluded that there was a decrease in the subjective pain score when checked by VAS score in patients treated with PRP and showed that there was an increase in function in the corticosteroid group at 3 weeks but at 6 weeks and 6 months there was an increase in function seen in the PRP group.^[9,19] Tsikopoulos et al. (2016) conducted a high quality systematic review/meta-analysis (MA) of RCTs (N =140) comparing the effect of steroid injections versus autologous whole blood injection on heel pain in patients diagnosed with PF. The authors concluded that although steroid injection was marginally more effective (reaching statistical significance) at 2-6 weeks after treatment, there was no significant difference at 24-26 weeks after treatment.^[20] The results of the current study show that females had higher pain scores than males at rest (before and after injection more than twice as well as slightly more in females than males when moving, many reports indicate the presence of many factors related to foot pain, and foot function, including footwear, general foot health and physical activity. This fact may be due to different shoes use, pain intensity, health status, or schedule physical activity, or social characteristics of both sexes. This result was similar to the study conducted by (Bytomski JR. et al),^[21] which may be reflected considering that the rate of pain related to gender showed that it is higher among females than males, with higher demand for treatment.

CONCLUSION

In this study we concluded that both PRP and corticosteroid injection therapy both provide symptomatic relief with potential effect to reduce pain and improve the functional outcome in cases of chronic planter fasciitis. The results found decrease in pain score in two groups at rest and movement but more among steroid groups than PRP group

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with statistically significant association in 10 days only after intervention ($p=0.02$) at movement.

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